

Germplasm improvement

Genetic resources

Search for seedborne endophytic fungi in rice

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A search was made for *Acremonium* spp. endophytes in the seeds of *Oryza* and related species. These endophytes occur in a symbiotic relationship with many grasses where they assist in the growth and persistence of their host. They are beneficial because the chemicals they produce make the grass more tolerant of drought, produce more tillers and seed, and enhance resistance to some pests and diseases. Infected grasses are symptomless and transmission of the fungus is only through mycelium in the seed. Usually all seeds from an infected plant contain mycelium.

The benefits could be considerable if such a fungus was present in rice. Seeds in the IRRI germplasm collection from

20 species of *Oryza* and 5 species in related genera collected from 31 countries were examined for the presence of endophyte mycelium. Seeds of *O. glaberrima*, *O. glumaepatula*, *O. rhizomatis*, and *O. schlechteri* were not available for testing. Seeds were softened by soaking overnight in 5% sodium hydroxide, then washed in water and boiled for 2 min in Garner's solution (50 ml lactic acid, 0.325 g aniline blue, 100 ml water). Seeds were then deglumed, squashed on a microscope slide, mounted in aniline blue, and examined with a microscope for the presence of endophyte mycelium. Single seeds from 20 to 100 plants were examined where possible, but for a few species, only 5-10 seeds were available. The species examined and the countries from where the seeds were collected are listed (see table). None were infected with endophyte mycelium.

It is unlikely that species of rice and related genera are infected with *Acremonium* endophytes. However, the possibility that some species may contain this endophyte cannot be ruled out entirely. ■

Species examined for the presence of *Acremonium* endophytes.

Species	Country of origin
<i>Oryza alta</i>	Brazil, India
<i>O. australiensis</i>	Australia
<i>O. barthii</i>	Guinea, Mali, Sierra Leone
<i>O. brachyantha</i>	Mali, Sierra Leone
<i>O. eichingeri</i>	Sri Lanka
<i>O. grandiglumis</i>	Brazil
<i>O. granulata</i>	India, Malaysia, Nepal
<i>O. latifolia</i>	Costa Rica, Guatemala
<i>O. longiglumis</i>	Indonesia
<i>O. longistaminata</i>	Benin, Côte d' Ivoire, Nigeria, Sierra Leone
<i>O. malampuzhaensis</i>	India
<i>O. meridionalis</i>	Australia
<i>O. meyeriana</i>	Malaysia
<i>O. minuta</i>	Philippines
<i>O. nivara</i>	Bangladesh, Cambodia, India, Myanmar, Sri Lanka, Taiwan-China, Thailand
<i>O. officinalis</i>	Malaysia, Myanmar, Thailand
<i>O. punctata</i>	Cameroon, Chad, Ghana, India, Kenya, Nigeria, Tanzania, Zaire
<i>O. ridleyi</i>	Thailand
<i>O. rufipogon</i>	Bangladesh, China, India, Malaysia, Papua New Guinea, Taiwan-China, Thailand
<i>O. sativa</i>	Bangladesh, India, Malaysia, Taiwan-China
<i>Chikusichloa</i> sp.	Japan
<i>Hygroryza aristata</i>	Sri Lanka
<i>Leersia perrieri</i>	Madagascar
<i>L. tisseranti</i>	Guinea
<i>Rhynchoryza subulata</i>	Argentina

Genetics

Genetic variation in chemical composition and digestibility of nutrients in rice straw

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The chemical composition and nylon bag organic matter digestibility (NBOMD) were determined for 24 straw samples from 21 varieties (Table 1). Twelve were grown in an agronomic trial in 1988 and 12 in a plant breeding trial in 1989. Sita, Pant Dhan 4, and Saket 4 were used in both years. All varieties were hand-harvested at 6-7 cm above the ground. Varieties were grouped according to their

Table 1. Rice varieties grouped according to nylon bag organic matter digestibility where A = high, B = medium, and C = low. 1988-89.

Group A	Group B	Group C
Saket 4 (2) IET8580	Narendra 2 Pant Dhan 4 (2)	Sita (2) VL 8
Narendra 118 Pant Dhan 6	Ratna Sarju 52	IET9362
UPR79-123 Manhar	IR8 IR24	
Jaya	VPR83-34 IET8111 IET8110 UPR-80-120 Govind	

NBOMD where A = high, B = medium, and C = low (Table 2).

After 72 h of incubation in fistulated rumens of cattle, the NBOMD varied

Table 2. Chemical composition (g/kg dry matter) and digestibility of nutrients (%) in rice straw. 1988-89.^a

Nutrient	NBOMD group		
	A High	B Medium	C Low
<i>Chemical composition</i>			
NDF	692	729	728
Hemicellulose	231	251	250
Cellulose	298	324	309
Crude protein	54	48	46
<i>Digestibility</i>			
Organic matter	53	50	45
Hemicellulose	52	52	45
Cellulose	48	48	42
	46	44	39

^aFigures are average values.

from 443 to 548 g/kg. A averaged 530; B, 501; and C, 453. Chemical composition in B and C was similar, so

the difference in NBOMD was because the neutral detergent fiber (NDF) in B degraded faster than in C. This was contributed by higher digestibility of cellulose and hemicellulose, the two components of NDF.

The difference between A and B was perhaps due to a combination of higher

neutral detergent solubles (NDS), higher crude protein (CP), and lower cell wall (NDF) contents for A. The higher NBOMD in A was attributed to the higher NDF ($r = 0.9$) and cellulose digestibility ($r = 0.7$) and CP content ($r = 0.66$). Varieties with lower NDF contained more CP.

The NBOMD of the three common varieties was similar during both years, indicating no year effect. The varieties were grown under the same agronomic conditions in the same soil, implying that the difference in NBOMD could only be because of their genetic makeup. ■

Heterosis in chemical composition and digestibility of rice straw

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The straw of 15 F_1 crosses and that of their 10 parents were collected from a rice breeding experiment. The chemical composition and nylon bag (72-h) dry matter digestibility (NBDMD) were determined for each (see table).

Crossing two varieties resulted in a hybrid with higher NBDMD than that of the parents, except for Narendra 118/Pant Dhan 6. Eliminating the cross with negative heterosis (Narendra 118/Pant Dhan 6) from heritability (h^2) estimation by regression gave h^2 values of 0.86 for NBDMD and 0.82 for nylon bag organic matter digestibility (NBOMD).

The crude protein (CP) content in most hybrids was greater than that of both or one of the parents. Both Narendra 118 and Pant Dhan 6 had

Chemical composition (%) and NBDMD (%) of rice straw from different parents and hybrids.

	Parents			Hybrids			
	CP	NDF	NBDMD	CP	NDF	NBDMD	NBOMD
IR58 ^a	4.2	70.1	47.1	—	—	—	—
UPR85-32	3.5	73.7	42.0	4.9	65.2	51.7	52.9 b
IET7566	4.6	66.4	46.3	4.9	69.5	49.9	51.0 ab
IET7613	4.7	68.6	49.9	5.4	68.2	54.6	55.7 c
UPR83-169	5.1	66.2	49.0	6.5	65.8	54.5	55.6 c
UPRH39	5.6	71.3	46.9	5.4	67.3	50.2	51.4 ab
Pant Dhan 6	5.3	69.3	49.3	5.8	67.6	53.8	54.8 c
Narendra 118 ^a	5.1	69.2	48.0	—	—	—	—
UPR82-43	3.6	72.1	41.2	5.3	66.9	49.8	51.1 ab
UPR85-32	3.5	73.7	42.0	6.0	67.7	50.7	51.8 b
IET7566	4.6	66.4	46.3	6.5	66.5	52.2	53.4 bc
IET7613	4.7	68.6	45.9	6.1	70.6	52.0	53.0 bc
Pant Dhan 6	5.3	69.3	49.3	4.7	68.1	47.9	49.0 a
IET6223 ^a	4.4	66.6	45.1	—	—	—	—
IET7566	4.6	66.4	46.3	5.3	66.7	51.2	52.3 b
IET7613	4.7	68.4	45.9	5.7	64.6	50.1	51.2 ab
UPRH39	5.6	71.3	46.9	5.4	68.5	49.7	50.9 ab
Pant Dhan 6	5.3	69.8	49.3	6.0	69.0	52.2	53.4 bc

^aIR58, Narendra 118, and IET6223 were crossed with the varieties grouped below them to produce hybrids.

relatively higher dry matter digestibility (DMD) and CP, so no further improvement could be expected in the hybrids.

Polygenes, the combination of which seem to be identical in these two varieties, may control the CP content.

The positive correlation between CP and DMD and the simultaneous reduction in the neutral detergent fiber (NDF) of hybrids are desirable for improving the nutritive value of straw. ■

Allelic relationship among fertility-restoring genes in rice

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We studied the allelism for the restoring gene(s) present in purified testers received from IRRI. The five testers, IR24 (T_1), IR54742-22-19-3 (T_2), IR29723-143-3-2-1 (T_3), IR9761-19-1 (T_4), and ARC11353 (T_5), were tested for

Segregation pattern of pollen and spikelet fertilities in test cross F_1 progenies. Tamil Nadu, India. 1992-93.

Test cross	Total plants observed (no.)	Pollen fertility ^a		Spikelet fertility ^b	
		Fertile	Sterile	Fertile	Sterile
V20 A ($T_1 \times T_2$)	200	169	31	169	31
V20 A ($T_1 \times T_3$)	200	200	—	200	—
V20 A ($T_1 \times T_4$)	200	175	25	174	26
V20 A ($T_1 \times T_5$)	200	200	—	200	—
V20 A ($T_2 \times T_3$)	200	165	35	167	33
V20 A ($T_2 \times T_4$)	200	200	—	200	—
V20 A ($T_2 \times T_5$)	200	168	32	166	34
V20 A ($T_3 \times T_4$)	200	178	22	178	22
V20 A ($T_3 \times T_5$)	200	200	—	200	—
V20 A ($T_4 \times T_5$)	200	161	39	163	37

^aPollen fertility = fertility \geq 60%, sterility = 0%. ^bSpikelet fertility = fertility \geq 80%, sterility = 0%.